

FAMILY FUNCTIONING AS CORRELATES TO PROSOCIAL BEHAVIOR AND AGGRESSION: BASIS FOR AN ENHANCED GUIDANCE PROGRAM

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Family Functioning as Correlates to Prosocial Behavior and Aggression: Basis for an Enhanced Guidance Program

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Abstract

The study aims to determine if family functioning is significantly correlated to prosocial behavior and aggression among junior high school students. A total of 206 respondents across two schools from the second district of Valenzuela, Metro Manila, served as the respondents and were selected through a random sampling technique. Three instruments were used: (a) the Family Assessment Device (FAD) which measures the healthiness of family functioning across six dimensions and one general functioning dimension, (b) the Prosocial Behavior Scale which assesses prosocial behavior through trust, and altruism, and agreeableness, and (c) the Buss-Perry Aggression Questionnaire which measures aggression through as a trait through four subtraits. The findings revealed that in terms of the dimensions of family functioning, two are within healthy levels, specifically, problem-solving, and roles, while the remaining dimensions of communication, affective responsiveness, affective involvement, behavior control, and general functioning are within unhealthy levels. Prosocial behavior, on the other hand, was found to be high among the respondents. And lastly, all subtraits of aggression were moderate. The dimensions of family functioning were revealed to have a significant negative relationship with prosocial behavior. This means that as problematic family functioning increases, prosocial behavior decreases. In terms of family functioning and aggression, all subtraits of aggression were found to have a significant positive relationship with dimensions of family functioning. This means that as problematic family functioning increases, aggression also increases. Lastly, in terms of prosocial behavior and aggression, no significant relationship was established. Based on the findings, different activities were proposed to provide enhancements to guidance program within the institutions.

Keywords: *family functioning, prosocial behavior, aggression, guidance program*

Introduction

Adolescence is a time of significant change, and as such is affected by people around them, especially the family systems. During this time, relationships within the family serves as an integral role in the socio-emotional development of the adolescent through guidance, monitoring, and supporting the personal development of the individual. The researcher, practicing as a guidance coordinator has observed the importance of family functioning as important aspects in the developing individual, especially in terms of one's attitude towards peers, such as trusting, collaborating, and helping other individuals, or even engaging in acts which may result in harm.

The initial concern was identifying the factors within the family which affected the development of such behaviors; thus the researcher considered the McMaster Model of Family Functioning (MMFF). The model consists of six major domains of family functioning, particularly, problem-solving, communication, roles, affective responsiveness, affective involvement, and behavior control. In addition to the major dimensions of family functioning, an overall concept of "healthiness" within the family systems is also considered, known as general family functioning.

With this, the assumption of effective problem-solving skills, proper and clear communications, proper role allocations, adequate affective responsiveness and involvement, and appropriate behavior control within the family systems as a factor which affected the development of prosocial and aggressive behavior was considered.

Prosocial behavior are actions towards the benefit of others or society, and has long been considered as virtuous behavior, and ethical standards within a given community. The act of helping not only benefits the receiver but have also been found to have the psychological benefits such as contributing to positive mood, reduced stress, & overall greater psychological wellbeing (Baumsteiger, 2019).

During adolescence, prosocial development is influenced by various factors, one of which is family functioning. Involvement and acceptance within the family were key factors in the development of prosocial behavior (Gao et al., 2019; Putnick et al., 2018). In addition to this, shared family values encourage children's participation in civic activities further reinforcing prosocial tendencies (Moran & Taylor, 2021). As prosocial behavior is something that is acquired (Buraghoain & Sonowal, 2016), programs may be developed opening avenues for the enrichment of the lives of not only adolescents, but also other stakeholders.

Aggression on the other hand are behaviors that result in harming oneself or others (Cherry, 2020). The importance of understanding teenage aggression as an issue of the family was indicated in various literature such as how proper family functioning is able to predict aggressive behavior (Naranjo & Caño, 2016), as well as how it can serve as preventative measures for developing further aggressive behavior (Dabaghi et al., 2018). As such, aggression then becomes an issue among parents, peers, and educators. It may be expressed in various ways such as being verbal and non-verbal, direct and indirect, as well as proactive and reactive forms (Wrangham, 2018). It may further lead to the violation of boundaries and subsequently the breakdown of relationship (Legg, 2019). Though aggressive is

often regarded as a negative characteristic, literature indicates that given proper management through effective programs, the behavior may be reduced (Oliveros-Peralta & Dominguez, 2020).

Having reviewed the literature, it is clear that the family serves a significant role in the development and wellbeing of an individual. Studies such as that of Borst (2015) indicate that the levels of family conflict is associated with the increase in risk-taking behavior of children, while the studies of Keyzers et al. (2019) and Holth (2015) has demonstrated as to how the family can serve as protective factors. Kapetanovic et al. (2020) further indicate as to how adolescent psychosocial functioning is mediated by the family's emotional climate, highlighting the importance of the family environment such as family communication and affective responsiveness as protective factors.

As such the effects of family functioning on the prosocial behavior of individuals are evident. The literature further points towards the family serving as a significant contributor to an individual's development. Studies such as that of Streit et al. (2020) and Orte et al. (2015) demonstrated as to how family conflict during toddlerhood can be a significant predictor of adolescent prosocial behavior, and as to how family competences and positive parenting are associated with prosocial behavior. Furthermore, Wu et al. (2016) demonstrated as to how children often learn prosocial behavior within the family context and practice through imitation.

In terms of family functioning and aggression, it has been observed that dysfunctional family functioning has been linked with increased problem behavior such as in Arshat et al. (2018) and Mirzaei et al. (2015), furthermore, issues in the quality of family relationship such as inappropriate communication (Durisic, 2018) and unstable family relationships (Coe et al., 2018) lead to increased externalizing behavior among adolescents.

Through this study, the researcher aims to address the pressing concerns of aggression among students, as well as the observed benefit of prosocial behavior exhibited by students by developing an enhanced guidance program which targets both the students in their stay within the institution, as well as families and other stake-holders. Writing this paper in the midst of the pandemic further highlights the importance of family research and how said family functioning affects the individual as the current situation further places much of the learner's socio-emotional development in the hands of the family systems (He, 2021).

By being able to enhance, and implement guidance programs, especially in preparation for the re-opening of schools, or even in the new-normal setting, the researcher believes that such programs may further aid in the socio-emotional development of the learner.

Research Questions

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the respondents' family functioning according to:
 - 1.1. problem solving;
 - 1.2. communication;
 - 1.3. roles;
 - 1.4. affective responsiveness;
 - 1.5. affective involvement;
 - 1.6. behavior control; and
 - 1.7. general functioning?
2. What is the respondents' level of prosocial behavior?
3. What is the aggression level of the respondents in terms of:
 - 3.1. physical aggression;
 - 3.2. verbal aggression;
 - 3.3. anger; and
 - 3.4. hostility?
4. Is there a significant relationship between family functioning and prosocial behavior?
5. Is there a significant relationship between family functioning and aggression?
6. Is there a significant relationship between prosocial behavior and aggression?

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a descriptive-correlational design in which it describes a phenomenon that is happening at a particular time, while attempting to establish a relationship between the variables presented in the study (Foranzo & Gravetter, 2017). Using standardized psychological tests, the research correlated the dimensions of family functioning to prosocial behavior and the subtraits of aggression among junior high school students.

Participants

The study was conducted in coordination with St. Joseph Academy of Valenzuela and Montessori Academy of Valenzuela, two non-sectarian private secondary coeducational institutions within the second congressional district of Valenzuela city.

To ensure that the sample size was representative of the population, the Slovin's formula was utilized at five percent (5%) margin of error wherein the total computed sample size for the sampling to be representative of the population was one hundred ninety-two (192). The total number of respondents was at two hundred and six (206), of which were aged 12 – 17, from grades 7 – 10 of either educational institution.

Instrument

The Family Assessment Device (FAD) is a 60-item standardized self-report measure that is based on the McMaster Model of Family Functioning (MMFF), which is an approach to evaluating and treating families (Mansfield, Keitner, & Archambault, 2017). The measure is designed to describe the structural and organizational properties of the family as well as the patterns of transactions which distinguishes healthy from unhealthy families. The dimensions of family functioning include (1) problem solving, (2) communication, (3) roles, (4) affective responsiveness, (5) affective involvement, (6) behavior control, and (7) general functioning (Epstein, Baldwin, & Bishop, 1983).

The Family Assessment Device scores represent the levels of healthy and unhealthy functioning per domain based on the validation study of the authors of the FAD (Miller, Bishop, Epstein, & Keitner, 1985), as well as the review of assessment tools for family therapy (Cottrell et al. 2018), Healthy levels for each dimension are as follows in which, problem solving (1.00 – 2.20), communication (1.00 – 2.20), roles (1.00 – 2.30), affective responsiveness (1.00 – 2.20), affective involvement (1.00 – 2.10), behavior control (1.00 – 1.90), and general functioning (1.00 – 2.00). For the unhealthy levels, it is as follows problem solving (2.21 – 4.00), communication (2.21 – 4.00), roles (2.31 – 4.00), affective responsiveness (2.21 – 4.00), affective involvement (2.11 – 4.00), behavior control (1.91 – 4.00), and general functioning (2.01 – 4.00).

Psychometric properties for the measure proves to be satisfactory, where reliability values were established to be at $\alpha = .74, .75, .72, .83, .78, .72, .89$ for the problem solving, communication, roles, affective responsiveness, affective involvement, behavioral control, & general functioning dimensions, respectively. In terms of validity, the scale was able to demonstrate discriminant validity by discriminating between clinical and non clinical samples (Epstein, Baldwin, & Bishop, 1983). Further validation studies such as that Mansfield, Keitner, & Dealy (2014) indicated that the instrument's psychometric properties are up to date where reliability estimates are at $\alpha = .75, .80, .70, .75, .74, .68, & .89$ for the problem solving, communication, roles, affective responsiveness, affective involvement, behavioral control, & general functioning dimensions, respectively.

The Prosocial Behavior Scale (PBS) by Caprara & Pastorelli (1993). It is a 15-item standardized measure that assesses a child's behavior of altruism, trust, & agreeableness. Further literature such as that of Mestre et al. (2017) indicate that it was used to measure helping behavior, trust, & sympathy in its study on young offenders & non offenders. The scale has been used in numerous international and local literature to measure prosocial behavior such as in the study of Caprara et al. (2000), Pastorelli et al. (2016), Mestre et al. (2017), & El Mallah (2018), furthermore, the scale was also identified by Vilar, García, & Soto (2019) in a systematic analysis of psychometrically sound measures of prosocial behavior.

The foundational literature of the prosocial behavior scale (Caprara & Pastorelli, 1993) did not indicate cut-off scores to discern high from low scorers. It simply indicated that the higher the score, the more it represents helping behavior, trust, and sympathy towards others (Mestre et al., 2017). To categorize the scores, three classes were created through uniform distribution. This means that the score ranges are within the bounds of the parameters of the minimum and maximum values divided by the number of classes (Glenn, n.d.). The levels are as follows: low (10 – 16.66), moderate (16.67 – 23.33), and high (23.34 – 30).

Psychometric properties for the measure is deemed to be satisfactory wherein the scale's internal consistency was established to be at $\alpha = .77 - .81$ for children ages 10 – 18 (Pastorelli et al., 1997; Pastorelli et al., 1997; Mestre et al., 2017).

The Buss-Perry Aggression Questionnaire (BPAQ) by Buss and Perry (1992), is a 29-item standardized measure that assesses an individual's level of aggression which is categorized into four subtraits. The first two subtraits, physical and verbal aggression, refer to the instrumental and motor component of aggressive behavior, in which how it is conveyed. The third subtrait, anger, refers to its physiological activation which represents the emotional and affective component of aggressive behavior. It is further emphasized in the study of Peralta, Pedrero, Bravo, and Giraldez (2014), that it implies psychological activation and prepares one for aggression. The fourth subtrait, hostility, refers to the feelings of ill will and injustice, which represents the cognitive component of aggression.

Buss & Perry (1992) did not provide a cut-off score to discern high and low scorers, however, the foundational literature as well as subsequent studies such as that of Dabaghi et al. (2018) indicated that to higher scores represent the characteristics of the particular subtrait and vice-versa. To account for this, uniform distribution was utilized. This means that the score ranges are within the bounds of the parameters of the minimum and maximum values divided by the number of classes (Glenn, n.d.). For physical aggression, the scores are as follows low (9.00 – 21.00), moderate (21.01 – 33.00), and high (33.01 – 45.00), for verbal aggression, the scores are as follows low (5.00 – 11.66), moderate (11.67 – 18.32), and high (18.33 – 20.00), for anger, the scores are as follows low (7.00 – 16.33),

moderate (16.34 – 25.66), and high (25.67 – 35.00), and lastly, for hostility, the scores are as follows low (8.00 – 18.66), moderate (18.67 – 29.32), and high (29.33 – 40.00).

Psychometric properties for the measure are deemed to be satisfactory. In the original literature of Buss & Perry (1992) internal consistency for individuals aged 18 - 20 was established to be at $\alpha = .85, .72, .83, \& .77$ for the physical aggression, verbal aggression, anger, and hostility subscales respectively, and $\alpha = .89$ for the overall scale. Further validation studies such as that of Santisteban & Alvarado (2009), in which internal consistency for individuals aged 9 – 11 and 14 – 17 was established to be at $\alpha = .80, .73, .65, \& .66$ for the physical aggression, verbal aggression, anger, & hostility subscales respectively using the Spanish validated instrument based on the original 1992 model.

Procedure

Upon the approval of the panel and the director of the College of Science Graduate Program, the researcher requested permission to conduct the study at both institutions from the respective school heads. Before proceeding to data gathering, the researcher requested permission for the use of the Prosocial Behavior Scale from the author, while both the Buss-Perry Aggression Questionnaire, and the Family Assessment Device were free to use for research purposes.

Data gathering was conducted through Google Forms, an online data gathering platform which was formatted to accommodate the questionnaires of the study. The survey questionnaires were provided to the respondents during an online synchronous schedule using Google Meet, an online video-conferencing platform to ensure the authenticity of the respondents, as well as to facilitate any questions or clarifications posed by the respondents. Prior to the administration of the questionnaires, the informed consent was read to the respondents to discuss the aspects of the study which includes the details of the study, confidentiality, and the voluntary nature of participation.

Data Analysis

To answer the research questions, the arithmetic mean, an average in which scores are considered of equal weight, was utilized to determine the levels of family functioning, prosocial behavior and aggression. In addition to this, Spearman's rank correlation was utilized to describe the relationship between family functioning, prosocial behavior, and aggression as the assumption of normality for the Pearson's correlation was not met by all variables.

Ethical Considerations

The study was conducted within ethical standards. To ensure that the rights of the respondents were protected, formal approval was obtained from the university research panel in conducting the study, as well as the participating institutions. The respondents were informed about the objectives of the research, its benefits, and potential risks. Prior to the gathering of the data, the respondents were informed regarding their confidentiality and the right to opt out of the study. In addition to this, the Google Forms link also reiterated the abovementioned information subject to the respondent's willingness to participate.

Results and Discussion

This presents the data gathered as well as discuss the interpretation, relationships, and reasons for its occurrence. The tables show the present values that will help in the discussion of the results.

Table 1. *Level of family functioning*

<i>Family Functioning</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Problem Solving	2.10	0.53	Healthy
Communication	2.51	0.42	Unhealthy
Roles	2.30	0.34	Healthy
Affective Responsiveness	2.44	0.43	Unhealthy
Affective Involvement	2.48	0.49	Unhealthy
Behavior Control	2.27	0.29	Unhealthy
General Functioning	2.15	0.52	Unhealthy

Healthy: Problem Solving (1.00-2.20) Communication (1.00-2.20) Roles (1.00-2.30) Affective Responsiveness (1.00-2.20) Affective Involvement (1.00-2.10) Behavior Control (1.00-1.90) General Functioning (1.00-2.00)
Unhealthy: Problem Solving (2.21-4.00) Communication (2.21-4.00) Roles (2.31-4.00) Affective Responsiveness (2.21-4.00) Affective Involvement (2.11-4.00) Behavior Control (1.91-4.00) General Functioning (2.01-4.00)

Table 1 reveals that among the dimensions of family functioning, only problem solving, and roles fall within healthy levels with a mean score of 2.10 (SD = .53), and 2.30 (SD = .34) respectively. This means that the respondents can solve problems which may arise within the family and deal with them in effective ways, as well as maintain roles and responsibilities which maintain family functioning. Conversely, communication, affective responsiveness, affective involvement, behavior control, and general functioning fall within unhealthy levels with a mean score of 2.51 (SD=.42), 2.44 (SD=.44), 2.48 (SD=.49), 2.27 (SD=.29), and 2.15 (SD=.52). This means that the respondents receive and send messages unclearly and indirectly, are not properly expressing emotion within the family appropriately, are uninvolved with the concerns, activities, and problems of other family members, and do not adhere to behavioral standards within the family.

Table 2. Levels of prosocial behavior

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Prosocial Behavior	24.0	3.07	High

Low: 10.00-16.66 Moderate: 16.67-23.33 High: 23.34-30

Table 2 reveals that among the respondents of the study, prosocial behavior is high with a mean score of 24.0 (SD=3.07). This means that the respondents exhibit helping behavior, trust in others, altruism, and agreeableness. This suggests that the respondents respond to other individuals who are in need of help, they are willing to trust and cooperate with their peers, as well as to show acts of kindness towards others.

Table 3. Level of aggression

Family Functioning	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Physical Aggression	25.1	5.97	Moderate
Verbal Aggression	14.9	3.58	Moderate
Anger	20.2	4.88	Moderate
Hostility	26.0	5.71	Moderate

*Low: Physical Aggression (9.00-21.00) Verbal Aggression (5.00-11.66) Anger (7.00-16.33) Hostility (8.00-18.66)
Moderate: Physical Aggression (21.01-33.00) Verbal Aggression (11.67-18.32) Anger (16.34-25.66) Hostility (18.67-29.32)
High: Physical Aggression (33.01-45.00) Verbal Aggression (18.33-20.00) Anger (25.67-35.00) Hostility (29.33-40.00)*

Table 3 reveals that among the respondents, all subtraits of aggression are within moderate levels with a mean score of 25.1 (SD=5.97) for physical aggression, 14.9 (SD=3.58) for verbal aggression, 20.2 (SD=4.88) for anger, and 26.0 (SD=5.71) for hostility. It must be noted that for physical aggression, verbal aggression, and anger, scores lean towards the moderately low levels meaning that there is a lesser tendency and frequency of physically harming others, being disagreeable and argumentative, and being easily physiologically and emotionally aroused towards aggressing others. On the other hand, hostility scores lean towards the moderately high levels meaning that the respondents have a higher tendency and frequency to have feelings of ill-will, suspicion, jealousy, and bitterness towards others.

Table 4. Correlation between family functioning and prosocial behavior

Family Functioning	Prosocial Behavior				
	r	Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Conclusion
Problem Solving	-.316	Weak negative correlation	.000**	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Communication	-.129	Very weak negative correlation	.065	Accept H ₀₁	Not Significant
Roles	-.136	Very weak negative correlation	.051	Accept H ₀₁	Not Significant
Affective Responsiveness	-.119	Very weak negative correlation	.088	Accept H ₀₁	Not Significant
Affective Involvement	-.005	Very weak negative correlation	.946	Accept H ₀₁	Not Significant
Behavior Control	-.069	Very weak negative correlation	.322	Accept H ₀₁	Not Significant
General Functioning	-.224	Weak negative correlation	.001**	Reject H ₀₁	Significant

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Table 4 depicts the relationship between family functioning and prosocial behavior using the Spearman’s rank correlation test. Based on the table, there exists a significant negative correlation between prosocial behavior and family functioning, particularly prosocial behavior and problem-solving where $r=-.316$ ($p<0.00$), and prosocial behavior and general functioning where $r=-.224$ ($p<0.001$).

The results indicate that problematic problem-solving has a weak negative correlation with prosocial behavior. This means that as problematic family functioning increases, prosocial behavior decreases. This implies that when the respondents and their families actively collaborate, support, and help each other resolve issues amongst themselves, these behaviors translate to kindness, cooperation, and assistance toward others as well.

These results are supported by Streit et al. (2020) which indicated that conflicts within the family are negatively associated with prosocial behavior, further indicating that supportiveness within the family allows for the development of prosocial behavior. This is further supported by Orte et al. (2015) indicating that an association exists between prosocial behavior, parent-child relationship, family involvement, and positive parenting. As such involvement allows for members of the family to be collaborative and engage in positive activities further allowing the development of prosocial behavior.

In terms of general functioning, as unhealthy family functioning increases, prosocial behavior decreases. As indicated, general functioning does not serve as a specific dimension of family functioning but is instead a gauge of the overall health of the family. Nevertheless, general family functioning serves as a factor which affects prosocial behavior among individuals. This association may be due to the individual’s evaluation of how a healthy and functional is supposed to manifest trust, altruism, and helping others. This is supported by Gao et al. (2019), in which family functioning was positively associated with prosocial tendencies. Implications towards practice may include giving emphasis on enhancing family functioning through programs to lessen emotional and conduct problems while increasing prosocial behavior as indicated by Arshat et al. (2018). Other possible avenues for approach may be through programs which focus on one’s self-esteem such as mindfulness programs as self-esteem has been observed to be indirectly associated with prosocial tendencies through family functioning (Gao et al., 2019).

Table 5 depicts the relationship between family functioning and physical aggression using the Spearman’s rank correlation test. Based on the table, there exists a significant positive correlation between family functioning and physical aggression, particularly, a weak

positive correlation with communication where $r=0.238$ ($p<0.001$), affective responsiveness where $r=0.261$ ($p<0.000$), affective involvement where $r=0.347$ ($p<0.000$), behavior control $r=0.222$ ($p<0.001$), and general functioning where $r=0.356$ ($p<0.000$), and a very weak positive correlation with roles where $r=0.205$ ($p<0.003$).

Table 5. Correlation between family functioning and physical aggression

Family Functioning	r	Physical Aggression			
		Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Conclusion
Problem Solving	0.113	Very weak positive correlation	0.107	Accept H_{02}	Not Significant
Communication	0.238	Weak positive correlation	0.001**	Reject H_{02}	Significant
Roles	0.205	Very weak positive correlation	0.003**	Reject H_{02}	Significant
Affective Responsiveness	0.261	Weak positive correlation	0.000**	Reject H_{02}	Significant
Affective Involvement	0.347	Weak positive correlation	0.000**	Reject H_{02}	Significant
Behavior Control	0.222	Weak positive correlation	0.001**	Reject H_{02}	Significant
General Functioning	0.356	Weak positive correlation	0.000**	Reject H_{02}	Significant

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

The results indicate that problematic family functioning is positively correlated with physical aggression. This means that the lack of clarity and directionality of communication, the inability to fulfill roles and responsibilities, the inability to properly express emotions, the lack of emotional involvement, and the inability to adhere to the behavioral standards within the family has been observed to be associated with manifesting direct aggression as a means of expressing oneself. As such, these may be due to the feelings of frustration becoming pent up as it is not properly communicated within the family (Naranjo et al., 2016; Dabaghi et al., 2018) leading to an explosion of emotion through physical aggression. Furthermore, when duties and responsibilities are left unattended, friction may arise within the family as consistent with the findings of Gerlach (2015) causing increased externalizing behavior (Durisic, 2018).

In addition to this, emotional response and involvement are seen as important components of family functioning as neglecting these areas lead to increased instances of physical aggression which may be due to inconsistent communication (Kapetanovic et al., 2020), insecure attachments hindering emotional responsiveness (Al Ubaidi, 2017; Wydra et al., 2017), and the lack of guidance in terms of appropriate behavior (Elham, 2016; Hennenberger et al. 2016, & Mirzaei et al. 2015)

When it comes to behavior control, the lack of control within the family and the inability to meet and adhere to behavioral standards are associated with physical aggression. This may be due to parenting styles in which too strict parenting such which leads to restriction of freedoms may lead to frustration and eventually aggression.

These findings are supported by Dabaghi et al. (2018) in which poor family functioning may lead to higher levels of aggressive behavior. Though higher levels of behavior control may lower physical aggression, the type of control must be considered properly, as Malonda et al. (2019) indicated that highly strict parenting-styles may further increase aggression levels among adolescent, while rejecting parenting-styles (uncaring) may also result in rebellion (Olson et al., 2019).

Table 6. Correlation between family functioning and verbal aggression

Family Functioning	r	Verbal Aggression			
		Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Conclusion
Problem Solving	-0.075	Very weak negative correlation	0.283	Accept H_{02}	Not Significant
Communication	-0.033	Very weak negative correlation	0.639	Accept H_{02}	Not Significant
Roles	0.202	Very weak positive correlation	0.004**	Reject H_{02}	Significant
Affective Responsiveness	0.007	Very weak positive correlation	0.918	Accept H_{02}	Not Significant
Affective Involvement	0.195	Very weak positive correlation	0.005**	Reject H_{02}	Significant
Behavior Control	0.253	Weak positive correlation	0.000	Reject H_{02}	Significant
General Functioning	0.076	Very weak positive correlation	0.279	Accept H_{02}	Not Significant

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Table 6 depicts the relationship between family functioning and verbal aggression using the Spearman's rank correlation test. Based on the table, there exists a significant positive correlation between family functioning and verbal aggression, particularly, a very weak positive relationship with roles, where $r=0.202$ ($p<0.004$), affective involvement, where $r=0.195$ ($p<0.005$), and a weak positive relationship with behavior control, where $r=0.253$ ($p<0.000$).

The results indicate that problematic family functioning is positively correlated with verbal aggression. This means that the inability to meet one's roles and responsibilities within the family, being emotionally uninvolved, and the inability to adhere to the behavioral standards within the family are associated with higher levels of verbally aggressive behavior.

This implies that such inability to meet said needs in the family can cause discontent and frustration which can lead to being argumentative with other individuals. These findings are consistent with Al Ubaidi (2017) and Dabaghi et al. (2018), indicating that such inability to fulfill the roles and needs within the family lead to its dysfunction, as well as that of Mirzaei et al. (2015) and Elham (2016), indicating that involvement within the family and monitoring one another helps regulate verbally aggressive behavior.

Table 7. Correlation between family functioning and anger

Family Functioning	Anger				
	r	Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Conclusion
Problem Solving	-0.006	Very weak negative correlation	0.929	Accept H ₀₂	Not Significant
Communication	0.129	Very weak positive correlation	0.065	Accept H ₀₂	Not Significant
Roles	0.276	Weak positive correlation	0.000**	Reject H ₀₂	Significant
Affective Responsiveness	0.143	Very weak positive correlation	0.040*	Reject H ₀₂	Significant
Affective Involvement	0.272	Weak positive correlation	0.000**	Reject H ₀₂	Significant
Behavior Control	0.130	Very weak positive correlation	0.062	Accept H ₀₂	Not Significant
General Functioning	0.250	Weak positive correlation	0.000**	Reject H ₀₂	Significant

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed),

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Table 7 depicts the relationship between family functioning and anger using the Spearman’s rank correlation test. Based in the table, there exists a significant positive correlation between family functioning and anger, particularly, a weak positive correlation with roles, where $r=0.276$ ($p<0.000$), affective involvement, where $r=0.272$ ($p<0.000$), and general functioning, where $r=0.250$ ($p<0.000$), and a very weak correlation with affective responsiveness, where $r=0.147$ ($p<0.040$).

The results indicate that problematic family functioning is positively correlated with anger. This means that when duties and responsibilities within the family are left unattended, emotions are not properly expressed, and members of the family are not emotionally involved, anger increases. This leads to feelings of discontent and frustration which may lead to individuals to be easily irritated and feeling as if they want to explode with all of their pent-up emotions. This highlights as to how the family serves as a contributor to the emotion regulation of the individual. These are consistent with Margareta et al. (2021), indicating as to how dimensions of family functioning affect emotion regulation, which is further consistent with Dabaghi et al. (2018) indicating that dysfunctional roles in the family can lead to higher aggressive behavior which is further supported by Gerlach (2015) and Al Ubaidi (2017), indicating that such lack of rules, regulations, and expectations may cause anger and eventually lead to more instrumental forms of aggression.

Emotional responsiveness as well as emotional involvement within the family were also exhibited to affect aggression, in which Kapetanovic et al. (2020) observed that the affective responsiveness within the family may allow for support and has been associated with emotional and conduct problems, as well as delinquency and wellbeing. In addition to this, since anger is the feelings towards aggressing others, having a cohesive family functioning allows proper support and monitoring from the family (Elham, 2016).

Table 8. Correlation between family functioning and hostility

Family Functioning	Hostility				
	r	Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Conclusion
Problem Solving	-0.005	Very weak negative correlation	0.940	Accept H ₀₂	Not Significant
Communication	0.125	Very weak positive correlation	0.074	Accept H ₀₂	Not Significant
Roles	0.146	Very weak positive correlation	0.037*	Reject H ₀₂	Significant
Affective Responsiveness	0.163	Very weak positive correlation	0.019*	Reject H ₀₂	Significant
Affective Involvement	0.199	Very weak positive correlation	0.004**	Reject H ₀₂	Significant
Behavior Control	0.172	Very weak positive correlation	0.014*	Reject H ₀₂	Significant
General Functioning	0.215	Weak positive correlation	0.002**	Reject H ₀₂	Significant

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed),

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Table 8 depicts the relationship between family functioning and hostility using the Spearman’s rank correlation test. Based on the table, there exists a significant positive correlation between family functioning and hostility. Particularly a very weak positive correlation with roles, where $r=0.145$ ($p<0.037$), affective responsiveness, where $r=0.163$ ($p<0.019$), affective involvement, where $r=0.199$ ($p<0.004$), behavior control, where $r=0.172$ ($p<0.014$), and a weak positive correlation with general functioning, where $r=0.215$ ($p<0.002$).

The results indicate that problematic family functioning is positively correlated with hostility. This means that as roles and responsibilities become neglected, family members are not emotionally involved, unable to express themselves appropriately, and do not adhere to the behavioral standards expected of them, hostility increases. These feelings of ill-will can be attributed to the feelings of discontent and frustration which leads to conflict leading to negative feelings towards others. These findings are consistent with Gerlach (2015) indicating how such inability to satisfy roles and responsibilities within the family is a primary source of conflict, Ubaidi (2017) indicating that the inability to meet the physical and emotional needs of family members are causes of dysfunctional family functioning. The results further imply that in terms of affective responsiveness, and involvement, the appropriateness of the expression of emotion as well as the involvement of family members in each other’s lives help improve family climate and decrease the levels of hostility among individuals. (Kapetanovic et al., & 2020; Elham, 2016).

Table 9 depicts the relationship between prosocial behavior and aggression using the Spearman’s rank correlation test. Based on the table, there is no sufficient statistical evidence to prove that prosocial behavior, and aggression are significantly correlated.

Table 9. Correlation between prosocial behavior and aggression

Aggression	Prosocial Behavior				
	<i>r</i>	Interpretation	<i>p</i> -value	Decision	Conclusion
Physical Aggression	-.122	Very weak negative correlation	.080	Accept H ₀₃	Not Significant
Verbal Aggression	.091	Very weak positive correlation	.192	Accept H ₀₃	Not Significant
Anger	-.108	Very weak negative correlation	.121	Accept H ₀₃	Not Significant
Hostility	-.041	Very weak negative correlation	.557	Accept H ₀₃	Not Significant

Among the possibilities for the lack of significant relationship may be in that prosocial behavior is not simply due to the presence or lack of self-regulation, indicating that there may be other factors at play. This is supported by Streit et al. (2020), in which their study suggested that the manifestation of prosocial behavior was due to the suppression of negative impulses while aggression was the opposite, meaning the lack of its suppression.

This contradictory finding then indicates that prosocial behavior is not simply the opposite of aggression, but other factors also affect the manifestation of both behaviors. One such avenue for exploration is empathy, in which the idea of thinking of the perspectives and feelings of others may be factors as to why people help one another and not the lack of aggression and/ or negative feelings for others. This is supported by Kou et al. (2018); and Overgaauw et al. (2017) indicating that empathy serves as a significant factor that affects prosocial behavior as this component allows the individual to consider the feelings of others (affective empathy) and think about the perspectives of others (cognitive empathy). In addition to this, the study of Mestre et al. (2017) further supports the notion of empathy as a factor, in which even though their study showed that high levels of prosocial behavior can predict lower levels of aggression and vice versa, their results indicated that empathy was the strongest predictor of prosocial behavior. Lastly, environmental factors may also serve as factor in the manifestation of aggressive or prosocial factors, as individuals especially children and teens spend significant amount of time among each other. This is supported by Osbuth et al. (2015) in which even though high levels of prosocial behavior predicts lower levels of aggression and vice-versa, peer rejection was revealed to be mediating variable for lower levels of future prosocial behavior, in which past aggression may lead to peer rejection which in turn leads to lower instances and opportunities of manifesting prosocial behavior.

Conclusions

The findings of the current study yielded information in understanding the family functioning, levels of prosocial behavior, and aggression among the respondents. The study provides new insight for future researchers interested in learning the relationship between family functioning, prosocial behavior, and aggression. Based on the summary of findings, the researcher has come up with the following generalizations:

There is a significant relationship between family functioning and prosocial behavior indicating that healthy family functioning increases prosocial behavior as the collaboration and involvement within the family allows for the development of trustfulness, altruism, and helping behavior.

There is a significant relationship between family functioning and aggression indicating that unhealthy family functioning increases aggressive behavior as the inability of families to satisfy its needs such as basic and personal development needs, the involvement among one another, the appropriate affective responsiveness among one another, and the enforcement and adherence to behavioral standards may all lead to the development of physically and verbally aggressive behavior, as well as anger and hostility.

There is no significant relationship between prosocial behavior and aggression indicating that there may be other factors that affect the development of both behaviors among adolescents.

In line with the findings of the study, the following are recommended: The inclusion of family functioning assessment as part of the enhanced guidance program of the institution. The inclusion and implementation of the enhanced guidance program and activities to sustain improve the unhealthy family functioning, and moderate levels of aggression, and sustain the high levels of prosocial behavior. Training of teaching personnel in handling homeroom guidance activities relevant to improving family functioning, sustaining prosocial behavior, and lessening aggression. Collaboration with the school administrators such as the principal, and other executives in the implementation of the enhanced guidance program such as through approval and funding of said programs and activities. Collaboration with the families as part of the program to promote healthy family functioning. Future researchers may consider looking into topics on attachment and empathy as both factors have been of note during the literature review.

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